

Gibberellin-induced parthenocarpy in fruits of a prickly pear mutant

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Table S1. List of primers used in this study.

No.	Gene name	Primer (Forward/Reverse)
1	KAO	CCTGGTGATCTGGGTTTGCC CCGTCTTGCCAAACCTGGTG
2	GA13ox	CAAAAGGGTTCGCTCCAAGC CCAGTTGGGTCATCCGAAGG
3	GA3ox	AAATCCCACACTATGCCCGC CCCATTTGAACGAGTCGGGT
4	GA20ox	GGCCGGATGTGTTCCGATTA CGTCGACCCCTCTTCAATCC
5	GA2ox	GGGGCAGTATCAGAGTTGGC GGAGGATGGAGTCGCTTTGG
6	GID	GACGTGCCCCTGAAAACAGA CCACCCGAACTATCACCTGC
7	SCL1	TGGGGTAAGCCCATCTCCTG CGGGCCCTATAACCACCTCA
8	SCL13	CCCTTTGGGAAATGGAGGGC GATAATCCTGCACCCGCACC
9	SCL21	ATGGCAGGGTTCCGACAGTA TGAAGCCGAAACCAGCATCC
10	Ty3/Gypsy1	TTTCAAGGAGGTGCCGATCC GTCCCCCACCAGTATTCAGC
11	Ty3/Gypsy2	CTTGTATCCCAGAAGCGCGA AGGGCCAGCTTCCTAGATCA

Figure S1. Ovule fresh weight (OFW), ovule dry weight (ODW) and flower bud weight in BS1 and revertant flowers. Ovules were harvested from flower buds at pre-anthesis (A&C) and during anthesis (B&D). Data are presented as means \pm SE (n=10) and were analyzed using Student's t-test. Asterisks denote a statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

Figure S2. Shape index and weights of BS1 and revertant flower buds during pre-anthesis and anthesis. Numbers on the fruit denote value of the shape index. Data are presented as means \pm SE (n=10) and were analyzed using Student's t-test. The asterisks denote statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

Figure S3. Length, diameter, and weight of BS1 and revertant flower buds during pre-anthesis (A) and anthesis (B). Data for 10 fruits are presented as means \pm SE (n=10) and were analyzed using Student's t-test. The asterisks denote statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

Figure S4. Transcriptome analysis: **A** Bar plot for read counts data showing the variations in read counts between the BS1 and revertant (Rev) groups; **B** Box plot showing a comparative analysis of data dispersion within and between the BS1 and revertant groups for transformed data distribution; **C** Density plot of transformed data showing the differences in data distribution between the BS1 and Rev groups; **D** Phylogenetic tree showing the genetic relationships between BS1 and Rev groups; **E** Scatter plot of transformed expression in BS1 and Rev, showing a strong positive relationship; **F** Volcano plot of differentially expressed genes.

Figure S5. Differential expression of genes in BS1 and revertant (Rev). **A** PCA analysis showing the significant pattern of variation between BS1 and Rev; **B** Total number of DEGs between BS1 and Rev; **C** Mean-Absolute (MA) plot showing DEGs. Log-fold change between BS1 against the mean (M) expression across all Rev samples (A); **D** Hierarchical clustering of DEGs shows the gene expression pattern and relationships between BS1 and Rev samples.

